

CREATIVE INDUSTRIES OF TOURISM ENTERPRISES AS A FACTOR IN DESTINATION DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract

The article is devoted to the systematisation of information and to substantiating the role of individual substantive components of creative industries that are applied in practice by tourism enterprises differing in technological profile, location, and scale of activity, in the development of regional tourism destinations and in enhancing the tourism attractiveness of a territory. For each of the seven identified profile types of enterprises involved in receiving tourists, the main directions and specific features of the use of elements and characteristics of each of the five groups of creative industries, according to the UNCTAD classification, are determined. It is established that the use by such enterprises of key elements of creative industries, including traditional and contemporary art, cultural heritage, innovative approaches and technologies for the creation and market promotion of products and services, media industries, fashion, and others, makes it possible not only to reliably ensure their own competitiveness but also to significantly strengthen the overall local tourism potential, thereby contributing to the growth of tourism popularity and visitor numbers in the region. Park hotels and rural tourism homesteads are identified as particularly important focal points for attracting tourists to a region.

Keywords: creative industries; tourism enterprises; tourism destinations; regional tourism image; regional tourism attractiveness.

Problem statement. Creative industries, as a key manifestation of the nexus between creativity and business under contemporary conditions, are increasingly considered and utilised in many countries as a powerful factor in the development of the economy and culture, the enhancement of investment attractiveness, and the advancement of society based on the principles of sustainable development. A particularly important direction for the implementation of the concept of creative industries into business practice is the tourism sector, which, alongside its economic role, performs the functions of a cultural and environmental driver and a social vector of development for many communities. However, in our view, under current conditions the role of creative industries in ensuring a positive tourist image and enhancing tourist attractiveness for many regions and localities, with the gradual formation of tourism destinations, remains insufficiently substantiated; this process is driven primarily by the creative initiative of local tourism entrepreneurship, with the support of government authorities and civil society institutions. Therefore, the systematisation of information and the assessment of the significance of creative industries in the development of tourism destinations of various profiles and levels under contemporary conditions can be considered relevant and timely.

Analysis of recent research and publications. In numerous scholarly and popular works in the fields of tourism, economics, and management, attention is devoted to the influence of creative industries on the formation of a positive regional tourism image. Emphasis is also placed on the consolidated role of local business, public authorities, education, science, and the general public in applying these industries as an additional factor contributing to a territory's tourism attractiveness.

As examples, one may refer to the works of S. Benhaida [2], L. Safaa [2], D. Perkumienė [2], G. Labauska [2], M. Lusticky [3], M. Musil [3], S. Pavliuk [5], among others.

However, in most cases, these studies merely declare and partly explain this role in a generalized manner, without specifying the degree of this influence with respect to the nature of creative industries. Furthermore, they lack detailed specification of the types of enterprises and other actors that employ creative industries in promoting tourist visits to specific localities.

The purpose of the article is to systematise information and to substantiate the role of individual substantive components of creative industries that are applied in practice by tourism enterprises differing in technological profile, location, and scale of activity, in the development of regional tourism destinations and in enhancing the tourism attractiveness of a territory.

Presentation of the main material. An analysis of numerous definitions of creative industries makes it possible to interpret them as types of economic and cultural-artistic activities in which a creative approach to product creation for subsequent consumption is most vividly manifested. In scholarly, educational, instructional-methodological, and popular literature, numerous classifications and groupings of creative industries can be found, developed primarily according to their substantive profile and the scale of activity. The subsequent analysis in this study is based on the classification of the United Nations Conference on Trade and Development (UNCTAD) [1], which is widely implemented in practice in many countries.

The range of tourism enterprises, and accordingly their classifications, is also quite broad, with prevailing criteria including their substantive and technological profile and the scale of activity. In this study, within the context of influencing the tourism attractiveness of a territory and the formation of tourism destinations as elements of regional and local branding, consideration is given only to enterprises providing inbound tourism services to visitors from other localities, regions, and countries, actively demonstrating various characteristics of hospitality. Outbound tourism enterprises, located at significant distances from the focal locality, contribute to the formation of tourism destinations only

indirectly, by increasing visitor numbers and, consequently, expanding their popularity. A key role in such formation is played by local tourism business initiatives, encouraged by local authorities and the public. The use of elements and characteristics of creative industries within such initiatives significantly enhances both the commercial and image-related success of the enterprises themselves and the local and regional tourism attractiveness [1;4;7].

By correlating the potential of creative industries, as defined by the UNCTAD classification, with the specific features of the technological specialization of local tourism enterprises based on the established sectoral division of tourism, we identified the key directions and specific features of the use of elements and characteristics of each of the five groups of creative industries for each of the seven types of enterprises involved in tourist reception. These findings are presented in general terms in Table 1. It is therefore appropriate to proceed with a component-by-component analysis of this table.

Table 1

**Use of creative industries by tourism enterprises
as a factor in the development of tourism destinations**

Profile types of enterprises	Creative industry groups according to UNCTAD				
	Cultural heritage	Arts	Creative services	Media industries	Functional creativity
Local tour operators and travel agencies	Inclusion of cultural heritage sites in tour itineraries	Use of performance elements in tour accompaniment	Use of modern IT technologies in product promotion	Educational media products about tour destinations (films, brochures, etc.)	Inclusion of creative products in tourist souvenirs
Local transport services	Use of traditional means of transport for sightseeing	Artistic stylisation of vehicles based on specific creative concepts	Creative advertising of tourism transport services	Media products presenting opportunities and experiences of tourist transportation	New designer solutions for interior design
Excursion service providers, museums	Inclusion of cultural heritage sites in excursion programmes	Theatrical excursions, museum sessions, and quests	Original stylistic approaches to excursion delivery and promotion	Dissemination of media content about excursions and visitor facilities	Inclusion of creative products in souvenirs for visitors
Health, wellness, and resort establishments	Familiarisation with traditional local treatment methods	Artistic spatial design and organisation of cultural events	Use of modern IT technologies in promoting health and wellness services	Dissemination of media content on medical, wellness, and related services	Distribution of designer products made from environmentally friendly materials
Entertainment and performance venues	Use of elements of local classical and folk creativity in event scenarios	Original artistic approaches to organising performances and entertainment	Non-standard design solutions and IT technologies in event preparation, promotion, and implementation	Online streaming, reports, and individual media products of the venue	Use of original creative products and new crafts in events, taking fashion trends into account
Accommodation and food service enterprises (hotels, restaurants)	Use of heritage elements in guest space design and service delivery	Artistic solutions in spatial design and provision of core and additional services	New design technologies and promotion of hotel and restaurant products	Media products highlighting the specificity of the establishment in the context of territorial uniqueness	Workshops on producing and selling original creative products
Local organisers of sports and adventure tours	Inclusion of historical and natural landmarks and panoramic views in routes	Artistic approaches in tour preparation and tourist guidance	Innovative solutions in promoting tours with an emphasis on a healthy lifestyle	Media content on the benefits and experiential aspects of tours	Use of innovative materials and equipment in instruction and tourist support

Source: compiled by the author based on [1]

Enterprises of the tour operator and travel agency sector, which specialise in the development and commercialisation of tourism products, including tourist routes and detailed travel itineraries, within the region of their location and which operate for local residents as well as for tourists from other regions and foreign countries, are primarily oriented towards the application of creative approaches in both the design and the promotion of such routes and itineraries. In their practical activities, these enterprises actively incorporate creative solutions aimed at enhancing the attractiveness and distinctiveness of tourism products.

In particular, this involves the inclusion in tour itineraries, arranged in a well-considered and logically structured sequence, of visits to the most interesting, expressive, and distinctive objects and elements of local heritage. Such heritage may include movable and immovable assets, as well as material and intangible components, which in many cases may initially be little known or insufficiently popular due to the limited awareness of potential consumers. In addition, tour operators and travel agencies increasingly apply non-traditional techniques of group accompaniment, integrating elements of performance and interactive engagement in the process of accompanying tourist groups, thereby enhancing the emotional and experiential dimension of tourism services.

A significant role is also played by the utilisation of original advertising tools and public relations instruments in the promotion of tourism products. This includes the use of so-called “fantasy advertising” and other creative communication techniques in promoting tours on both local markets and geographically remote markets. Furthermore, these enterprises are actively engaged in the creation and dissemination of informational and promotional media materials related to their tourism products. Such materials encompass both audiovisual content and printed media, serving not only promotional purposes but also educational and popularisation functions with respect to the tourism destinations and routes offered.

In addition to the above, it may be recommended that enterprises operating within this sector introduce the practice of producing branded small souvenir items as corporate compliments, that is, as symbolic “gifts” for tourists. These souvenirs may incorporate the visual and symbolic identity of the enterprise, the specific tourism product, as well as the localities and attractions included in the tour itinerary, thereby strengthening brand recognition and creating lasting associative links with the destination.

Each of the subsequent sectoral types and groups of local tourism enterprises employs creative industries belonging to the relevant substantive blocks according to a generally similar scheme and orientation, while at the same time taking into account their own sectoral specialisation, functional focus, and operational characteristics. In the present case, as well as in the subsequent cases examined in this study, creative industries function not merely as instruments for ensuring the competitiveness of individual enterprises. They also actively contribute to the formation and reinforcement of regional and local tourism image and branding. This

multifunctional role of creative industries constitutes a distinctive feature of tourism, which clearly differentiates it from many other production and service sectors of the economy [1;2;3;4;5;6;7].

For local transport enterprises, the specific nature of transport use in tourism lies in the duality of its functional purpose, namely as a means of transportation and, at least partially, as a source of entertainment, since tourists are interested not only in “getting to a destination” but also in the experience of “riding” itself. This dual function creates a broad scope for the application of creative approaches. Such approaches include the use of traditional and authentic types of transport for sightseeing and leisure rides; the stylisation of both interior (passenger cabin) and exterior design of vehicles through various traditional and contemporary artistic solutions; the development of creative advertising specifically for tourist transportation services that combines elements of comfort and exotic appeal; as well as the production and dissemination of corresponding informational and educational popular media products, among other creative practices.

Enterprises operating in the excursion and museum sector of tourism largely represent creative industries in their own right, which naturally determines the extensive use of diverse creative approaches in their activities. These include the broad application of original forms for presenting cultural heritage phenomena and objects, incorporating elements of the atricalisation and quest-based experiences; non-traditional approaches to advertising services and producing educational and popular media content; and the organisation of workshops aimed at popularising traditional craft practices, among other forms of creative engagement [1;2;3;4;5;6;7].

Enterprises and institutions of the health, wellness, and resort sector, although their activities are to a considerable extent constrained by specific medical regulations and prescriptions, are nevertheless able to employ creative and unconventional approaches in shaping resort and recreational spaces, organising leisure activities for visitors, and advertising and informing audiences about the healing properties of the locality and the history of resort development. Since resort services are based not only on local natural healing resources but also on the environmental purity of the surrounding area, it is appropriate to propose the production and distribution of souvenirs bearing the symbolism of the establishment and the resort, made from environmentally friendly materials using traditional and authentic technologies [1;2;3;4;5;6;7].

Enterprises and institutions engaged in entertainment and performance activities, alongside museums, are traditionally included in creative industries regardless of whether they formally belong to the tourism sector. However, when providing services specifically to tourists, as opposed to local residents, these establishments are entrusted with the important mission of contributing to the formation of a local tourism image and the overall perception of the territory by visitors. This responsibility encourages the manifestation of additional creative efforts, including the use of elements of local classical culture and folk creativity in the scripts

of performances and show programmes; the application of original artistic techniques in organising entertainment and performance events; and the implementation of non-standard design solutions and digital technologies in the preparation, promotion, and execution of such events, taking current fashion and cultural trends into account [1;2;3;4;5;6;7].

Enterprises and institutions of the hotel and restaurant sector of tourism, which were initially oriented towards satisfying basic physiological human needs such as sleep, food, and hygiene, have over time evolved into a powerful service industry characterised by the extensive application of creative ideas. These ideas relate to the directions, forms, methods, and stylistic approaches used in the design and decoration of guest spaces, in service procedures and operational processes, and in the promotion of services among potential guests. However, with regard to their contribution to the overall tourism attractiveness of a region, manifestations of creativity in hospitality business practices should be aligned with local specificity, traditions, and the general cultural atmosphere of the area, including local cuisine and other elements of authenticity [1;2;3;4;5;6;7].

Enterprises, institutions, and business entities specialising in the organisation and implementation of sports-oriented tourism activities, including hiking and various forms of “extreme” tourism (such as parachuting, diving and rafting, surfing, paragliding, and similar activities), are, on the one hand, limited in their creative expression by tourist safety requirements. On the other hand, they possess significant opportunities to promote visits to local sites and areas, primarily of natural origin, thereby making a substantial contribution to regional tourism attractiveness and the formation of tourism destinations [1;2;3;4;5;6;7].

Finally, within the context of the issues examined in this study, special attention should be given to such specific local hospitality enterprises and establishments as rural tourism homesteads and park hotels. As a rule, these facilities occupy relatively large areas and are characterised by a high degree of service integration, combining and synthesising features of the excursion and museum sector, the hotel and restaurant sector, health and recreational services, and, to some extent, transport, entertainment, and sports-extreme tourism activities. In our view, such enterprises act as the main “tourism magnets” of any region and represent distinctive “regional focal points of tourism attractiveness”, that is, independently formed tourism destinations. In certain cases, such establishments emerge in locations that were previously completely unsuitable for recreation; for example, by creating flourishing gardens with high-quality recreational spaces on former landfill

sites, made possible exclusively through the creative ideas and initiatives of their founders [1;2;3;4;5;6;7].

Conclusions. Overall, the formation of tourism destinations and the enhancement of the general popularity and positive tourism image of a region are significantly supported by enterprises, institutions, and business entities of various service profiles that are oriented towards the reception and servicing of tourists within the localities and areas of their operation. The use by these actors of key elements of creative industries, including traditional and contemporary art, cultural heritage, innovative approaches and technologies for the creation and market promotion of products and services, media industries, fashion, and related fields, makes it possible not only to reliably ensure their own competitiveness but also to substantially strengthen the overall local tourism potential, thereby driving growth in tourism popularity and visitor numbers in the region. Park hotels and rural tourism homesteads constitute particularly important focal points for attracting tourists to a region.

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